

SIGNIFICANT ROLE OF PHYTOCONSTITUENTS IN HERBAL FORMULATIONS FOR ANALGESIC AND ANTI INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY

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Abstract: - Plant-derived materials and herbal medicines are gaining a lot of attention these days because of their many uses, as plants with medicinal properties are the primary supplier of the bioactive substances used in traditional as well as contemporary medicine. Even in places where availability of modern medicine is available, there has been a notable increase in interest in and utilization of herbal remedies in recent years. There is a need for effective pain and inflammation treatment in today's world. Investigations into herbal formulations from natural sources are needed to find new treatment solutions. Assessing the analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties is the current study's objective along with pharmacological screening methods and the herbal formulations. The herbal preparations used in the aforementioned studies provided excellent discomfort and swelling prevention in test animals. The aforementioned pharmacological impacts may be attributable to the presence of phytoconstituents present in the formulations.

Keywords: Indomethacin, Tridax procumbens, Acetic acid, Carbopol, Triethanolamine.

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Introduction:

When treating pain pharmacologically, the World Health Organization (also known as the WHO) has developed a three-step analgesic ladder that contains additional medications in addition to analgesics and opiates for each type of pain.

- **Mild pain** -When needed, utilise acetaminophen, aspirin, and other nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs.
- **Moderate pain** - Use a mild Opioid, like codeine or hydrocodone, if the pain worsens or increases.
- **Severe pain** - In case the pain lasts longer than expected or is initially moderate to severe, administer a potent opioid, such as morphine, fentanyl, or meperidine. You have two options for managing your pain: continue using a non-opioid medication or cease.

Analgesics:

A class of drugs known as analgesics is given to patients to alleviate pain without compromising consciousness. The word's roots are the Greek terms a (without) with algein (pain). The central and peripheral nervous systems are both impacted by analgesic drugs. An analgesic, or painkiller, is a drug that treats or lessens pain. This is especially true of pain relievers like paracetamol. Also used in analgesics are nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), such as ibuprofen.

Types of analgesics: Analgesics include all prescription and over-the-counter painkillers that contain drugs such as Opioids opiates, and nonopioid substances. Many To attain the intended therapeutic

effect, nonopioid and nonopioid-opioid formulations also function as antipyretics and anti-inflammatory drugs.

Opioid receptors are found in both the peripheral tissue originating from both neural and non-neural sources and the brain's nervous system. Opioid receptors are concentrated heavily in the regions of the central regions of the brain are the rostral ventral medulla, locus cereleus, and periaqueductal grey (PAG). The layer of tissue in the dorsal horn known as the substantia gelatinosa contains opioid receptors as well. Activation of MOP receptors in the midbrain is thought to be one of the main causes mediating opioid-induced pain through the central nervous system. Here, MOP agonists indirectly stimulate descending inhibitory pathways that impact simultaneously periaqueductal grey (PAG) & nucleus reticularis paragigantocellularis (NRPG), ultimately leading to the activation of descending inhibitory neurons. As a result, the substantia gelatinosa in the dorsal horn directly connects to the nuclei raphe magnus (NRM), increasing neuronal traffic and activating 5-HT and enkephalin-containing neurons. Consequently, the thalamus receives less nociceptive input from the peripheral nervous system.

Exogenous production and endogenous Opioids can also directly inhibit the substantia gelatinosa (found in the dorsal horn) and peripheral nociceptive signal afferent neurons, reducing the transmission of nociceptive signals from the periphery. This series with cellular events and activities generates most of the relief from pain that is commonly noticed following the ingestion of MOP agonists. [1]

Important facts about opiates and Opioid:

- Opioids, opium metabolites, or opium-like substances, are drugs that have the same capacity to change pain perception and raise pain thresholds as opium.
- Opioids and opiates may cause respiratory issues and have antitussive effects, particularly in the elderly.
- Terminal diseases and acute pain ranging from moderate to severe are treated with opiates and Opioids.
- Strong painkiller abuse can lead to addiction and psychological dependence. For short-term usage, these analgesics are both safe and effective.
- Both chronic pains related to terminal conditions and severe, acute pain are continuously treated with opiates and Opioids.

Uses of analgesics: Opioids and opiates, that alter how pain is felt by imitating endorphins to block the neurological transmission of pain signals and raise pain threshold, can be used to treat sudden pain of medium to severe severity.

Adverse effects of analgesics: Side effects are often encountered during pharmaceutical pain management, apparently supporting analgesia with limiting opioid tolerance. Even while it is necessary for informed consent, explaining possible side effects could make a nocebo work better.

Two (range 1-4) was the average amount of freely recalled side effects from their pain medication, both previous and present. Patients reported unknown side effects, with an average of zero (range 0-3) that may or may not have been brought on by analgesics. Some patients were capable of to identify more side effects when asked to read the prompt sheet that listed the most prevalent adverse effects associated with pain medication; these patients identified a standard deviation of 2 (in the range 1–8) side symptoms that they linked to their analgesics.

They have now discovered an additional mean of one (range 0-7) unidentified adverse effect. The 21 patients together reported 52 unique pain medication side effects, which could be divided into 18 different categories. They also listed forty-two unique adverse symptoms of unclear cause.

Three of the most frequently reported adverse effects associated with pain medication were fatigue/weariness (n = 8), constipation (n = 10), and dizziness (n = 8). The most frequent side effects of unclear cause were increased perspiration (n=5) and constipation (n= 8). Of the fifty-two side effects linked to painkillers, the majority (n = 25) were classified as severe, next to moderate (n = eighteen) and mild (n = 9). The majority (n = 16) of the 42 adverse effects with an unknown origin were classified as moderate, then mild (n = fourteen), and severe (n = 12). [2]

Inflammation: Inflammation, the way the body reacts to injury, sickness, or infection, assists to safeguard tissues. To initiate the inflammatory response, cells in the sick, injured, or infected tissue generate and release chemical compounds. These compounds cause loss of function, heat, soreness, redness, swelling, and discomfort. Leukocytes are attracted to the region of inflammation by additional signals provided by inflammatory tissues. Leukocytes clear wounded tissue of any toxic or infectious pathogens as well as cellular waste. This inflammatory response normally promotes recovery, but if unregulated, it could be harmful.

An inflammatory response may manifest as either acute or chronic. Usually, acute inflammation clears itself in a few days. Inflammation occurs if an incision becomes hot, red, hurts, or swells. Although the remainder of the immune system's machinery mobilises to heal, inflammation in this case acts to immobilise the damaged location. Inflammation is the body's primary line of defence towards damage or disease. The course of therapy treating acute inflammation, which includes administering aspirin along with various non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medicines to patients, lowers their discomfort and temperature. Contrary to popular belief, chronic inflammation may persist lasting a few months, weeks, or longer while harming the tissue.

❖ **Chronic inflammation:** In cases of long-term inflammation, the infection, injury, or disease takes the place of the original cause of inflammation as the issue. Persistent tissue inflammation persists in producing signals that extract leukocytes from the circulation.

The inflammatory response is heightened when leukocytes from the circulation penetrate the tissue. This prolonged inflammatory reaction may cause harm to good tissue in an attempt to heal and repair that will never work. Chronic inflammation is a feature of many illnesses, such as lupus and Crohn's disease.

❖ **Inflammation and disease chronic pathogenesis:**

- A hereditary predisposition is the root cause of a number of issues; include pancreas inflammation ulcerative colitis, and various rheumatic disorders.
- Others are connected to harmful bacteria that can evade the immune systems' removal of them from tissues. For instance, uncontrolled hepatitis B and C virus infections are linked to chronic hepatitis, while the gram-negative bacteria *Helicobacter pylori* causes chronic gastritis for infected hosts.
- Chronic physical or chemical pollutants, that involve acid reflux disease or UV radiation exposure, as well as toxic chemicals like asbestos or smoking, can potentially cause untreated inflammation.
- Other potential causes of chronic inflammation include polymorphisms or polymorphisms in important genes that control leukocyte survival, metabolic processes, and cytokine activity.
- Innate immune cells serve as the body's initial line of defence during acute inflammation and control the generation of adaptive immune responses. On the other hand, during prolonged inflammation, the above functions may be reversed, leading to a persistent, inappropriate stimulation of immune cells that are innate as a consequence of adaptive immunological responses.
- A variety of situations, including a viral infection, trauma, surgery, blister tissues infarction, or advanced cancer, might set off an inflammatory cascade. Symptoms that constitute an acute inflammatory response include micro vascular arterial dilation of (congestion), bloodstream protein discharge (oedema), along with additional local inflammatory reactions.
- Chemoattraction, local leukocyte activation, releasing of many mediators, and phagocytosis—the elimination of foreign items;

- Tissue repair and apoptosis, the termination of recruited cells. The majority of the immune system's acute response to inflammation is made up of cytokines that acute-phase proteins, and leukocytes.
- ❖ **Acute inflammation:** Inflammation is present when the wound appears hot, painful, red, and swollen. In this situation, inflammation serves a useful purpose by immobilising the injured area until the remaining portion of the immune system's response takes over. Acute inflammation often resolves within a few days and promotes recovery. The body uses inflammation as its main defence mechanism against harm or illness. In order to manage acute inflammation, patients are given aspirin and other non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medications, which reduces their discomfort and body temperature. By contrast, chronic inflammation can last for weeks, months, or even longer while damaging the tissue.

Pathogenesis of acute inflammation:

Innate immune cells serve as the initial line of defence and control the generation of adaptive immune responses during acute inflammation. However, these roles may be inverted during chronic inflammation, leading to a persistent, inappropriate development of immune cells that are innate as a result of adaptive immunological responses. Regardless of the fundamental originating cause, persistent the host inflammatory reactions can exacerbate chronic tissue damage that can result in systemic issues and major organ dysfunction, if a pathogenic or causing damage the agent isn't sufficiently eliminated from tissue and stays there or when a tissue is consistently damaged and insulted and fails to recover in a timely manner. Many conditions, including as infection, trauma, surgery, blisters being present, tissues infarction, and advanced malignancies, can set off an inflammatory cascade. The immediate reaction to inflammation at the local level comprises:

- Chemoattraction & local stimulation in leukocytes, release of several mediators, leukocyte adhesion to endothelium,
- Phagocytosis, the elimination of foreign substances
- Apoptosis, or the removal of recruited cells,
- Tissue repair are just a few of the processes that occur during capillary vessel vasodilatation (congestion).
- Acute-phase proteins, cytokines, and leukocytes are the three main components of the body's acute inflammatory response. The body's reaction to local inflammation is known as the acute-phase response,
- It is characterised by fever, increased hormone synthesis, including that of hydrocortisone and adreno-corticotrophic hormone (ACTH), increased production of white blood cells, and the liver's synthesis of acute-phase proteins. Most often secreted by activated tissue macrophages, including inflammation-associated mediators interleukin-1 (IL)-1, tumour necrosis factors (TNF)-, IL-6, which interferon (IFN), converting growth factor (TGF), and IL-8, increase the production of acute-phase proteins. The primary effector cells during acute inflammation are innate immune system neutrophils and monocyte/macrophages. [3]

Screening methods for analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities:

In vivo methods for analgesic activity:

A. Acetic acid induced writhing response in mice: The writhing caused by acetic acid inhibition method was used to assess the peripheral analgesic efficacy of several PHR extracts. The Swiss albino mice used in this experiment were prescreened and then split into groups. Oral administration of the extracts with (150 and three hundred mg=kg of body weight was done. The plant extracts' ability to prevent mice from writhing was compared to that of aminopyrine, a common painkiller, which is administered oral beginning at a dosage of 50 mg/kg. To induce pain perception, 0.1 ml (10 g) of 0.7% acetic acid was injected intraperitoneally (i.p.). Ten minutes following the acetic acid injection, the total number of writhes was counted. It was estimated to find the pain protection %.

The following formula was used to determine the percentage of writhing that was protected by the test and standard medications. [4]

$$\text{Percent protection} = 100 - (X_t / X_c) \times 100$$

Where, X_t = mean quantity of writhes within the treatment cohort;

X_c = mean quantity of writhes in control group.

B. Hot-plate latent pain response test in mice: Every female rodent was placed on a hotplate that was heated to 55°C how it responded to discomfort. Paws were licked, and there was bouncing in response. The response latency was measured as the interval in seconds from the platform and the response. The mice with latency times of 30 seconds or less were eliminated. Following delivery of the test samples of aspirin, Hcl morphine, and vehicle, the latency time was assessed at 30 and 60 minutes. The delay time will have to be reported as 60 seconds if the response period exceeds that amount. [5]

C. Formalin test: We utilised male Sprague-Dawley rats weighing between 250 and 300 g. The frequency of flinching and the amount of time spent licking or biting the injected hind paw in the early phase 1 (0–5 min after injection) and late phase 2 (20–60 min after injection) were recorded after injections of formalin (n = 8 in each group) or saline (n = 6 control). Five sham-injection rats (n = 5) had the needle inserted subcutaneously, but nothing was injected. [6]

D. Xylene-induced ear edema in mice: The xylene-induced ear edoema test was carried out in accordance with earlier instructions. A single dosage (125, 250, or 500 mg/kg) of either AEAPR or MEAPR, indomethacin (10 mg/kg), or vehicle (10 ml/kg) was administered intraperitoneally to each mouse one hour before to the induction of ear edoema through the topical administration of 0.02 ml a solvent such as on the inner and outer surfaces of the right ear. The control ear was the left ear. Mice (six per group) were slaughtered by cervical dislocation one hour after xylene was applied. Five millimeter circular portions were removed and weighed. We determined the weight differential between the animal's right and left ear portions in order to assess the degree of ear edoema. [7]

In vivo methods for anti-inflammatory activity:

A. Carrageenan-induced rat paw edema: The Winter et al. approach was used to evaluate the anti-inflammatory activity of

1% Carrageenan (in 1% CMC) solution was injected into the right hind paw subplantar area of all group rats. Normal saline was given to the first group, which was designated as the control. Oral gavage was used to provide *B. serrata* at low, mid, and high doses (50, 100, and 200 mg/kg/BW), respectively. The fifth group was given oral gavage of indomethacin (10 mg/kg/BW), which was the conventional treatment. Prior to receiving a one-hour injection of carrageenan, the rats were given various dosages of *B. serrata*, indomethacin, and normal saline. Paw edoema volume was determined by dislocating the fluid level using a Plethysmometer (UGO Basile, USA) at 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 hours following carrageenan injection. We assessed and compared average paw volume between the control group and standard groups. It was thought that the *B. serrata* treatment groups' reduced paw volumes in comparison to the control animals represented an anti-inflammatory response. [8]

The percentage of paw edema inhibition was calculated by using the following formula.

$$\text{Inhibition of Paw edema (\%)} = \frac{\text{Oc} - \text{OT}}{\text{Oc}} \times 100.$$

Where 'Oc' is edema volume of control group and 'Ot' is edema volume of treated groups. [9]

B. Acetic acid-induced capillary permeability: With some modifications, [10] the method was applied in this work to assess the extract's impact on blood circulation in adult mice with albino skin of both genders. The extract of methanol (100, 200, or 400 mg/kg) was given orally for one hour before 0.1 ml of Evans Blue dye (4% in normal saline) was injected intravenously through the tail vein. The animals in the vehicle control group were given similar doses of vehicle, while the animals in the group with a positive control received indomethacin (20 mg/kg). Animals were given an intraperitoneal shot of 0.4 ml of 0.5% v/v acetic acid thirty minutes later. After receiving an acetic acid injection, treated animals were sacrificed 30 minutes later, and the cavity of the peritoneum was cleaned with regular saline (5 ml) into tubes treated with heparin and centrifuged. Utilising the spectrophotometer and the wavelength of 590 nm, the dye quantity in the supernatant was determined.

Evans blue dye standard curve was used to calculate the amount of dye that seeped into the peritoneal fluid. Additionally, the percentage of inhibition was computed. [11]

In vitro methods for anti-inflammatory activity:

A. Anti-Lipoxygenase Activity: In the investigation of the anti-lipoxygenase test, linoleic acid served as the foundation with lipoxidase as the enzyme. After combining 0.25 milliliters of two million dollars borate solution (pH 9.0) with the test solution, 0.25 ml of diluted lipoxidase solution containing enzymes (20,000 U/ml) was added and then maintain for five minutes at 25°C. After adding and thoroughly mixing 1.0 milliliters of a 0.6 percent mM linoleic acid solution, the absorbance at 234 nm was measured. Indomethacin served as the baseline. The percentage inhibition was calculated using the following equation:

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = \left[\frac{\text{Absorbance of Control} - \text{Absorbance of Test Sample}}{\text{Absorbance Control}} \right] \times 100.$$

IC₅₀ values were calculated using a displayed dose response curve. The concentration necessary to achieve 50% of the permitted scavenging capability is referred to as IC. Every test and analysis was performed three times, and then averaged. [12]

B. Inhibition of Albumin denaturation: The blocking of protein denaturation technique was used to investigate the anti-inflammatory properties of a tiny amount of 1N HCL was used to alter the pH of the mixture that reacted containing the specimen extracts and 1% of the aqueous solution of the bovine albumin fraction. The sample extracts were heated to 51°C for 20 minutes after being incubated at 37°C for 20 minutes. The samples were then cooled, and the turbidity was measured in a UV-visible spectrophotometer at 660 nm. Three separate people carried out the experiment. The following formula was used to determine the percentage of inhibition of protein denaturation [13]

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = \frac{(\text{Abs control} - \text{Abs sample}) \times 100}{\text{Abs control}} \quad [14]$$

Phytoconstituents responsible for analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity:

Recently discovered analgesic and anti-inflammatory phytoconstituents include alkaloids, flavanoids, and terpenoids.

- **Role of flavanoids:** It is well known that flavonoids have anti-inflammatory and analgesic effects. These outcomes are linked to the stimulation of the antioxidants transcription factor Nrf2 and the suppression of pro-inflammatory cytokines that are dependent on NF-κB, including VEGF, ICAM-1, and STAT3. Numerous flavonoids, including vitexin and apigenin, have been shown to serve as safe natural alternatives to medicine for the treatment of inflammatory and analgesic conditions. Flavonoids have a wide range of activities since they are multi-target medicines. Tissues immunological cells that reside and immune cells that are recruited to the wounded tissues in an inflammatory response release a large number of mediators. PGE2, bradykinin, sympathetically amines, and cytokines that promote inflammation (e.g., TNF-, IL-6, and IL-1β) are some of the mediators that operate to either sensitise or activate nociceptors, which in turn elicit pain. The potential uses of flavonoids, which are chemicals derived from plants, as natural medicines has been increasing r time [15].
- **Role of Terpenoids:** Depending on their composition, the terpenoid-rich essential oils exhibit different anti-inflammatory and antinociceptive effects both in vitro and in vivo. They appear to have an effect apart from TNFα. A family of chemical substances known as terpenes is mostly found in plants and trees, including citrus fruit like lemon and mandarin, tea, cannabis, and thyme. These compounds exhibit appealing biological characteristics like analgesic and anticonvulsant effects. Additionally, a number of studies have shown that some terpenes may lessen the symptoms of inflammation by reducing the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as interleukin 1, tumour necrosis factor-alpha, and nuclear transcription factor-kappa B [16].
- **Role of alkaloids:** Since they were discovered several centuries ago, alkaloids have mostly come from natural sources and have been recognized for their significant qualities that have effects on biochemistry, pharmacology, and medicine in living things. Like other essential components for life in our bodies, alkaloids are produced from amino acids. Alkaloids are therefore regarded as having significant pharmacological value. Alkaloids are abundant secondary metabolites found in the leaves, stem, roots, and fruits of the plants that produce them. When taken and

administered in the appropriate amounts, they will be deadly and may even be fatal. The range of pharmacological activity is considerable. These are significant natural products that contain a variety of therapeutic plants, including ones that relieve pain [17].

Herbal formulations used for screening models: Design and evaluation of herbal formulations for analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity

S.NO	FORMULATIONS	MECHANISM
01	Hydro gel	The Polyherbal methanolic extract of ginger, turmeric, cinnamon, and capsicum was used to create this hydrogel formulation, which demonstrated strong analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties.
02	Oil formulation	The oily combination of thymol, methanol, and camphor suggested that monoterpenoids may be the cause of OFCMT's analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties.
03	Gel formulation	The study proved that gels based on Carbopol are effective. Thus, the prepared Polyherbal gels containing extracts of <i>Chenopodium ambrosioides</i> and <i>Chasmanthera dependens</i> show tremendous potential in the treatment of inflammation and pain.
04	Nanoemulgel	It was discovered that the nanoemulgel system exhibited thixotropic, pseudoplastic rheology behaviour. It was discovered that the DFS nanoemulgel performed better than the commercially available, traditional DFS gel. Diclofenac nanoemulgel formulation presents a viable delivery system for the treatment of inflammation and pain.
05	Creams	Areca catechu cream formulation would serve as a vehicle for the efficient and simple use of these therapeutic qualities in anti-inflammatory and wound-healing activities.
06	Ointments	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> ointment was utilised for its analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties.
07	Nanosuspension based gels	NS-HEC gels showed a notable and enhanced analgesic and anti-inflammatory effect as compared to the micronized etodolac and control groups. HEC gels based on ETD-NS show promise as a complementary treatment strategy for pain and inflammation.

Conclusion:

We would like to mention that these herbal formulations for analgesic and anti-inflammatory action were found to be powerful in the current work. Accordingly, herbal compositions demonstrate pronounced positive effects against models of cerebral, peripheral, and inflammatory pain. The existence of phytoconstituents may be responsible for this protective effect. We would like to draw the conclusion that it is important to consider using herbal formulations as medications, and that additional research should be done to determine the mechanism of action and conduct thorough phytochemical analyses to identify the active ingredients that exert analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity. These reports could be a first step in the investigation of substances with strong analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties.

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